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Editorial

Application of polymeric membranes and membrane processes in energy, environment, and medicine

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Over the past century, there have been some very useful applications in the field of science and technology with polymeric membranes (1). This issue of AICM covers the selected abstracts of papers presented at International Congress on Membranes & Membrane Processes (ICMMAP 2021) held during 12– 14, February 2021 at Mahatma Gandhi University, Kerala, India. ICMMAP 2021 brought together innovative academics and industrial experts in the field of polymer science & technology, materials science, environmental science, chemical engineering, biological sciences, and applied physics to a common forum. The primary goal of the conference was to promote research and developmental activities in membrane science and technology. This also aimed to promote scientific information interchange between scientists, researchers, students, and leaders from various fields such as materials science, chemistry, physics, biomedical engineering, polymer technology, electronics, automobile engineering, biotechnology, and other fields.

The congress was listened to by hundreds of researchers, doctors, and engineers, making it a grand success. Some of the selected abstracts of this issue cover a brief discussion on the application of porous silicon carbide ceramic membranes for the treatment of oily wastewater. Some other experts discussed the application of membrane processing technologies as a viable alternative to many traditional dairy processes like distillation, evaporation or extraction. One such presentation demonstrated the suitability of membrane technology in shrikhand (a popular Indian dessert from milk) preparation. One of the studies discussed the impact of ultra-confinement on the dilation of polymer films under supercritical carbon dioxide. Moly et al. presented the applicability of nanocomposite anion-exchange membranes in redox flow batteries. Lakra et al. presented their important findings on the use of integrated membrane processes the recovery of protein and carbohydrate from whey water. An interesting study investigated the separation potential of a bulk liquid membrane comprising of chemical species to recover organic acids from their dilute solutions. Nath and Reang showcased interesting research focused on an integrated ultrafiltration approach for the recovery of surfactant and potable water from domestic washing machine discharge. Some studies reported the use of anaerobic membrane bioreactor for zero-liquid discharge (ZLD) industrial processes. Yet, some others stressed the importance investigating the elementary transfers of electrons and/or protons using the principles of quantum-classical mechanics in the membranes of living cells.

Such deliberations emphasized the importance of developing novel membranes and appropriate membrane processes for a multitude of applications in energy, engineering and medicine. It is anticipated that the articles published in this issue of AICM will help to bring a meaningful change in scientific and technological research using membrane science and technology to fulfill the needs of society.

Keywords: *Membranes, membrane process, polymers, composites, blends*

References

1. Yusuf, A., Sodiq, A., Giwa, A., Eke, J., Pikuda, O., De Luca, G., ... & Chakraborty, S. (2020). A review of emerging trends in membrane science and technology for sustainable water treatment. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 266, 121867.

